

ANTHROPOMETRIC AND BIOLOGICAL MARKERS OF INSULIN RESISTANCE IN POLYCYSTIC OVARAY SYNDROME**¹*Dr. Prajakta Machale, ²Dr. Tinku-Ganesh Khalache**¹PG Scholar, Department of Prasuti Tantra and Stree Roga,²Associate Professor, Department of PG Studies in Prasuti Tantra and Stree Roga,^{1,2}Hon. Shri Annashaeb Dange Ayurvedic Medical College, Post Graduate and Reseaech Center, Astha.

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ABSTRACT

Polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) is one of the most common endocrine disorders, affecting 5%-10% of women of reproductive age. The importance of this syndrome lies in the magnitude of associated comorbidities: infertility, metabolic dysfunction, cardiovascular disease (CVD), plus psychological complications. Insulin resistance (IR) is a prominent feature of PCOS with a prevalence of 35%-80%. Without adequate management, IR with compensatory hyperinsulinemia contributes directly to reproductive dysfunction in women with PCOS. Furthermore, epidemiological data shows compelling evidence that PCOS is associated with an increased risk of impaired glucose tolerance, gestational diabetes mellitus and type 2 diabetes. In addition, metabolic dysfunction leads to a risk for CVD that increases with aging in women with PCOS. Indeed, the severity of IR in women with PCOS is associated with the amount of abdominal obesity, even in lean women

with PCOS. Given these drastic implications, it is important to diagnose and treat insulin resistance as early as possible. Many markers have been proposed. However, quantitative assessment of IR in clinical practice remains a major challenge. The gold standard method for assessing insulin sensitivity is the hyperinsulinemic euglycemic glucose clamp. However, it is not used routinely because of the complexity of its procedure. Despite this, many of them are either difficult to apply in routine clinical practice or useless for women with PCOS.

Considering this difficulty, there is still a need for an accurate marker for easy, early detection and assessment of IR in women with PCOS. This review highlights markers of IR already used in women with PCOS, including new markers recently reported in literature, and it establishes a new classification for these markers.

KEYWORDS: Markers; Insulin resistance; Polycystic ovary syndrome; Emerging markers; Impaired glucose tolerance.

INTRODUCTION

Polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) is the most common endocrine disorder, affecting 5%-10% of women of reproductive age. According to the Rotterdam consensus^[1], it is defined by at least two of the following abnormalities: oligo- and/or anovulation, clinical and/or biological hyperandrogenism, and polycystic ovaries. The importance of this syndrome lies in the magnitude of associated complications^[2,3]: Reproductive complications: menstrual dysfunction, infertility, hyperandrogenism, increased pregnancy complications, amongst others; Metabolic complications: insulin resistance and increased risk factors for type 2 diabetes (T2D) mellitus and cardiovascular disease (CVD); Oncological complications: Endometrial, ovarian and breast cancers; Psychological complications: Heightened anxiety, depression.

Insulin resistance (IR), the most common metabolic feature, is found in almost 35%-80% of PCOS women and is independent of body mass index (BMI) and body fat distribution.^[4-7] IR is usually defined as a pathological condition characterized by a decreased responsiveness or sensitivity to the metabolic actions of insulin. It is an established predictor of a range of disorders. In women with PCOS, IR plays an important role in the development and persistence of this disorder^[8,9] and is recognized to lead to many of the metabolic abnormalities associated with metabolic syndrome. PCOS patients with IR are likely to have chronic subclinical inflammation and impaired fasting plasma glucose levels, which in turn enhance the prevalence of the more atherogenic, low-density cholesterol (LDL- c) particles.^[10] Given this high prevalence, the need for accurate screening of IR in women with PCOS is obvious.

Early recognition and management of IR in women with PCOS would offer important preventive measures.^[10]

ANTHROPOMETRIC MARKERS

Anthropometry has been widely and successfully used for assessing health and nutritional risk. Several hundred papers have been published in the past five decades that have reported the close relation between different measures of body size and one or another cardiovascular risk factors.^[2-4] Most of them have attempted to assess the robustness and nature of these associations. Anthropometric markers could be divided into fat anthropometric markers and bone anthropometric markers. To date, bone anthropometric markers have been reported as the best anthropometric marker for insulin resistance.

BMI BMI is the ratio of weight to the square of height, initially described by Keys in 1976.^[3] BMI has traditionally been the chosen method to measure body size in epidemiological studies. It is used as a measure of overall adiposity and a good marker of variability in energy reserves in individuals with a sedentary lifestyle.^[3] Over the years, BMI has been shown to be an accurate marker for detecting cardiovascular risk. BMI > 25 kg/m² is a major risk factor for a wide range of chronic diseases and metabolic abnormalities, including T2D and IR, In women with PCOS, BMI is an independent predictor of IR; however, it is not routinely used as a surrogate marker of IR. Indeed, since IR in PCOS is independent of body fat, it could not accurately be predicted by BMI in lean PCOS women. BMI correlates more closely with IR in overweight and obese women than in lean PCOS women.

Waist circumference: According to the World Health Organization (WHO), waist circumference (WC) is measured at the approximate midpoint between the lower margin of the last palpable rib and the top of the iliac crest.

WC is an easy surrogate marker of visceral adiposity and is commonly used in daily medical practice to detect IR clinically. Increased visceral adiposity is associated with a range of metabolic abnormalities, including decreased glucose tolerance, reduced insulin sensitivity and adverse lipid profiles, which are risk factors for T2D and CVD. Moreover, WC is the core component of the definition of metabolic syndrome. It is specifically required for diagnosing metabolic syndrome according to the International Diabetes Federation and the 2003 Rotterdam consensus. A considerable correlation has been found between WC and insulin resistance assessed by the hyperinsulinemic euglycemic clamp technique. A wide WC > 80 cm has been shown to be associated with IR in women with PCOS. Therefore, WC is now considered the most clinically relevant approach for the measurement of IR.

However, the use of WC, a fat anthropometric marker, for the assessment of IR in women with PCOS is limited because IR is independent of visceral adiposity.^[5,7] Several studies have failed to show an association between WC and IR in lean women with PCOS.^[5] WC could predict IR in overweight and obese PCOS women but not in lean PCOS women.^[5] Consequently, it is not a good anthropometric surrogate marker for assessing IR in women with PCOS.

Waist-to-hip ratio: The waist-to-hip ratio (WHR) is an anthropometric index that combines waist and hip measurements. It is used as a measure of body fat distribution. According to the WHO, WHR is calculated as waist circumference divided by hip circumference.^[4] WHR > 0.8 corresponded with a BMI overweight range of 25-29.9 kg/m². Since it measures abdominal obesity, which in turn is attributed to the presence of visceral adipose tissue that promotes insulin resistance, WHR is used as a predictor of IR and metabolic risk. However, it has been described in several papers as a less accurate marker of adiposity that could predict cardiovascular and metabolic risk.

BIOLOGICAL MARKERS

Fasting insulin: Numerous studies have investigated and proposed fasting insulin concentrations as the simplest index for assessing IR^[8] because it has been shown to correlate well. High fasting insulin level in individuals with normal glucose tolerance has been found to reflect IR. Furthermore, high insulin concentrations presage the development of diabetes in the future.^[8] In nondiabetic subjects with normal fasting glucose levels, the rise of fasting insulin levels corresponds to insulin resistance. In this population, insulin sensitivity, which decreases as subjects become more insulin resistant, can be substituted by 1/fasting insulin. In women with PCOS, many authors have recommended fasting insulin as a simple office-based method to assess insulin resistance.^[7,8,9] Recently, after comparing the prevalence of IR using published methods in a cohort of women with PCOS, Lunger et al^[9], suggested the use of fasting insulin as a simple screening test. This can reduce the number of OGTTs needed to routinely assess IR in women with PCOS, as proposed by the Androgen Excess Society. However, the use of fasting insulin for assessing IR in women with PCOS could be limited by a lack of adequate laboratories and the cost of insulin assays, especially in developing countries.

Glucose/insulin ratio: The glucose/insulin ratio (G/I) has long been employed as an index of IR.^[4] It has been described by Legro et al, as a useful measure of insulin sensitivity in obese

PCOS women and has both high sensitivity and specificity for detecting IR in women. In addition, the G/I ratio reflects profound peripheral IR and hepatic IR, which are found in obese women.

Furthermore, Quon confirmed the same in his editorial published in 2004, explaining how the G/I ratio correlates with insulin sensitivity in nondiabetic patients with PCOS. In healthy subjects with normal fasting glucose levels, elevations in fasting insulin levels correspond to increased IR. Since fasting glucose levels are similar for all subjects, the G/I ratio is functionally equivalent to $1/\text{insulin}$, which is a well-known proxy for insulin sensitivity. It decreases as a subject becomes more insulin resistant and their fasting glucose rises. However, the use of the fasting G/I ratio is limited in PCOS women with abnormal fasting glucose levels because, as demonstrated by Quon, this leads to erroneous results. Indeed, the G/I ratio is similar to $1/\text{insulin}$ in nondiabetic subjects, but it increases paradoxically in diabetic subjects and in PCOS women with abnormal glucose levels. Consequently, the fasting G/I ratio has been considered a potentially flawed index of insulin sensitivity.

Markers using insulin and/or glucose Oral glucose tolerance test: The oral glucose tolerance test (OGTT) is a frequently used index of glucose tolerance. It is commonly used in medical practice to detect IGT and T2D.

Moreover, OGTT is the only means of identifying people with IGT. The WHO recommends the test as a valid way to diagnose diabetes. According to the WHO, the OGTT technique involves the oral administration of 75 g of glucose after 8 to 10 h of fasting. At 0, 30, 60 and 120 min following the oral glucose load, blood glucose levels are measured to determine how rapidly it is cleared from the blood stream. In PCOS women, the Androgen Excess Society in consensus with the European Society of Human Reproduction and Embryology (ESHRE) and the American Society of Reproductive Medicine (ASRM) have recently recommended a 2 h OGTT in all women with PCOS, with annual or biannual rescreening, depending on the risk factors.^[11] The Amsterdam ESHRE/ASRM-Sponsored 3rd PCOS consensus Workshop Group recommended screening for IGT and T2D when presented with the following conditions: hyperandrogenism with anovulation, acanthosis nigricans, obesity (BMI > 30 kg/m²) in women with a family history of T2D or gestational diabetes mellitus. However, OGTT provides useful information about glucose tolerance but not insulin resistance.

CONCLUSION

This article is an attempt to summarize existing markers of IR and their usefulness in women with PCOS. There is no recommended screening method for assessing IR in women with PCOS despite evidence of the high prevalence of this metabolic disturbance. A host of methods have been described for assessing insulin resistance. Each method has its own merits and disadvantages.

The euglycemic clamp remains the gold standard for direct measurement of insulin sensitivity. Concerning anthropometric markers, wrist circumference could revolutionize the assessment of IR in women with PCOS if validated through large-scale studies.

Finally, an easy-to-detect marker for assessing IR in women with PCOS is urgently required.

REFERENCE

1. Rotterdam ESHRE/ASRM-Sponsored PCOS consensus workshop group. Revised 2003 consensus on diagnostic criteria and long-term health risks related to Polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS). *Hum Reprod.*, 2004; 19: 41-47. [PMID: 14688154 DOI: 10.1093/humrep/deh098]
2. Bates GW, Legro RS. Longterm management of Polycystic Ovarian Syndrome (PCOS). *Mol Cell Endocrinol*, 2013; 373: 91-97. [PMID: 23261983 DOI: 10.1016/j.mce.2012.10.029]
3. Palomba S, Santagni S, Falbo A, La Sala GB. Complications and challenges associated with Polycystic ovary syndrome : current perspectives. *Int J Womens Health*, 2015; 7: 745-763. [PMID: 26261426 DOI: 10.2147/IJWH.S70314]
4. Carmina E, Lobo RA. Use of fasting blood to assess the prevalence of insulin resistance in women with Polycystic ovary syndrome. *Fertil Steril*, 2004; 82: 661-665. [PMID: 15374711 DOI: 10.1016/j.fertnstert.2004.01.041]
5. Dunaif A, Segal KR, Futterweit W, Dobrjansky A. Profound peripheral insulin resistance, independent of obesity, in Polycystic ovary syndrome. *Diabetes*, 1989; 38: 1165-1174. [PMID: 2670645 DOI: 10.2337/diabetes.38.9.1165]
6. Mayer SB, Evans WS, Nestler JE. Polycystic ovary syndrome and insulin: our understanding in the past, present an future. *Womens Health (Lond)*, 2015; 11: 137-149. [PMID: 25776288 DOI: 10.2217/WHE.14.73]
7. Amisi C, Mputu L, Mboloko E, Bieleli E, Pozzili P. [Biological insulin resistance in Congolese woman with Polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS)]. *Gynecol Obstet Fertil*,

- 2013; 41: 707-710 [PMID: 24200988 DOI:10.1016/j.gyobfe.2013.08.002]
8. Polak K, Czyzyk A, Simoncini T, Meczekalski B. New markers of insulin resistance in Polycystic ovary syndrome. *J Endocrinol Invest*, 2017; 40: 1-8. [PMID: 27473078 DOI: 10.1007/s40618-016-0523-8]
 9. Amato MC, Vesco R, Vigneri E, Cirese A, Giordano C. Hyperinsulinism and Polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS): role of insulin clearance. *J Endocrinol Invest*, 2015; 38: 1319-1326. [PMID: 26294351 DOI: 10.1007/s40618-015-0372-x]
 10. Singh B, Saxena A. Surrogate markers of insulin resistance: A review. *World J Diabetes*, 2010; 1: 36-47 [PMID:21537426 DOI: 10.4239/wjd.v1.i2.36]